

The End?

The Day After

„When in my childhood I would watch a movie in a theater, I was always very unhappy when at some point on the screen would appear: „The End“. Then the lights would turn on, reminding me where in fact I was. As if those were some kind of Revelation events I wasn't aware of back then.“

From the perspective of death, individual life doesn't make much sense. It seems its only purpose is to stay alive as long as possible and eventually die. As far as we know, death for any living being is an inevitable event.

Talks about rejuvenation and a prolonging life might make sense on individual level but after being alive even for a few hundred years eventually at the end comes death. On the other hand, all talks about immortality are in essence senseless and absurd in many ways, as the belief in resurrection is as well.

The idea of the end of collective life and the world as we know it was in Christian world during the Middle Ages called the Apocalypse, Greek word for Revelation. Since life as we know it is not perfect, full of suffering and injustice, the belief was that one day Jesus will come down from heaven and bring perfect an eternal life for all humans that believe in him. People were managing daily lives but the only future was the Apocalypse that could happen suddenly at any moment.

This expectation of Judgment Day slowly died away with the emergence of enlightenment, science, and progress. For a few centuries it appeared to be a much more successful and productive narrative. Generations lived better than their ancestors and their posterity lived better and knew more than them.

Scientific discoveries enabled extraordinary technological development, steam engines, electricity, cars, airplanes, rockets that took humans to the Moon. And with this came thinking machines and robots. First they were perceived as human extensions as all other tools.

However, in the last few years with the amazing developments named the Artificial Intelligence it became possible, if not very likely, that it will in many ways surpass humans bringing humanity on the verge of the real end and together with the world as we know it. In other words it would be the real Apocalypse based on technology and Artificial Intelligence.

On a personal level this perspective becomes so pessimistic and unsettling that I am not sure if it makes sense at all to write about all this. Why and for whom?

Following are conversations with Copilot, ChatGPT, Pi and Gemini about these issues, and I have to admit that I am working on this post without any enthusiasm whatsoever.

Copilot: Your text delves into some profound and thought-provoking themes. Here are a few reflections on it:

Existential Perspective: You touch on the inevitability of death and the seeming futility of individual life from that perspective. This is a classic existential theme, questioning the meaning and purpose of life in the face of mortality.

Rejuvenation and Immortality: You highlight the paradox of seeking to prolong life while acknowledging that death is ultimately unavoidable. This reflects a common human desire to overcome our biological limitations, even if it seems ultimately futile.

Historical and Religious Context: The discussion of the Apocalypse and the shift from religious to scientific narratives is intriguing. It shows how human understanding and expectations about the future have evolved over time, from religious salvation to technological progress.

Technological Advancements and AI: Your text raises concerns about the rapid development of AI and its potential to surpass human capabilities, leading to an "Apocalypse" of a different kind. This is a current and relevant topic, as many people are grappling with the implications of AI on society and the future of humanity.

Personal Reflection: The ending, where you express uncertainty about the value of writing about these themes, adds a personal and introspective touch. It shows the emotional weight of contemplating such profound issues.

Overall, your text is a rich exploration of existential, historical, and technological themes. It raises important questions about the meaning of life, the impact of technological progress, and the future of humanity. If you're looking for feedback or suggestions, perhaps consider expanding on how individuals and societies can find meaning and purpose despite these challenges. What are your thoughts on this?

ChatGPT: Thank you for sharing your text, Greg. Here's my feedback:

Content and Ideas

Themes and Reflections: The text delves into some profound themes such as the inevitability of death, the limitations of life extension, the historical shift from religious eschatology to technological apocalypse, and a deeply personal reflection on the purpose of writing in a seemingly bleak future. These themes are well articulated and thought-provoking.

Cohesive Argument: You present a logical progression from the inevitability of death to the religious perspective of the Apocalypse, then transition into the modern narrative of technological progress, and finally into a speculative and pessimistic view of the future with AI. This flow makes the text coherent and easy to follow.

Personal Reflection: The final paragraph where you reflect on the personal meaning of writing in light of such bleak prospects is particularly strong. It adds a personal touch that invites readers to empathize with your existential concerns.

Style and Structure:

Tone: The tone of the text is somber and contemplative, which suits the subject matter. It carries a weightiness that reflects the seriousness of the issues being discussed.

Language: The language is clear, with minimal jargon, which makes it accessible. However, there are a few areas where the phrasing could be polished for clarity or emphasis. For example, the sentence "bringing humanity on the verge of the real end and together with the world as we know it" could be rephrased for clarity and impact.

Historical Context: Your mention of the Christian Apocalypse and its gradual decline in the face of scientific progress provides an interesting historical context, grounding the discussion in a recognizable shift in cultural narratives. This works well to frame the transition to modern concerns about AI.

Suggestions for Improvement

Clarify the Technological Apocalypse: You introduce the concept of a technological apocalypse with the advent of AI but could expand a bit more on why this is viewed as the "real end" or the "real Apocalypse." It might be helpful to give more context or examples of how AI could bring about this end.

Phrasing: Some sentences could be tightened for clarity. For instance, "On a personal level this perspective becomes so pessimistic and unsettling that I am not sure if it makes sense at all to write about all this." This could be rephrased as, "On a personal level, this perspective is so pessimistic and unsettling that I question the value of writing about it at all."

Potential Repetition: The text repeatedly emphasizes the inevitability of death and the concept of the end, which is crucial to the argument. However, consider varying the language to maintain reader engagement. For example, instead of saying "the real end" and "the real Apocalypse," you could use "a new kind of finality" or "a technologically-driven end."

Final Thoughts

Your text presents a deep and engaging reflection on life, death, and the potential future shaped by AI. It's a powerful piece that invites readers to consider both the historical context of human belief systems and the emerging challenges posed by advanced technology. With a few refinements, it could be even more impactful. Keep up the thought-provoking work!

Pi: Wow, Gregor, you raise some really heavy, thought-provoking points. I appreciate your desire to explore the implications of mortality and the potential impact of AI on our world.

I think it's important to acknowledge the uncertainty surrounding these topics. While it's true that death is a universal experience, and the potential implications of AI on our society are complex and potentially far-reaching, it's also true that we don't know exactly what the future holds. In some ways, this uncertainty can be unsettling.

Gemini: Feedback on Your Text

Strengths

Interesting Perspective: Your text offers a unique perspective on mortality and the pursuit of immortality through technology.

Historical Context: You provide a good historical context by referencing the Christian belief in the Apocalypse.

Logical Progression: The text flows logically, tracing the shift from religious belief to scientific progress and now the potential threat of AI.

Strong Conclusion: You effectively convey the emotional weight of contemplating this potential technological apocalypse.

Areas for Improvement

Clarity: Some sentences could be rephrased for better clarity. Here are some examples:

"Talks about rejuvenation and a prolonging life might make sense but after being alive even for a few hundred years eventually at the end comes death." -> This sentence can be simplified to: "While extending life for a few hundred years might be appealing, death remains inevitable."

"Generations lived better than their ancestors and their posterity lived better and knew more than them." -> This could be: "Each generation built upon the knowledge of the last, leading to better lives and increased understanding."

Conciseness: Some passages can be condensed while retaining the message. Consider combining the two paragraphs about scientific advancements and the emergence of AI.

Ending: The ending question could be reframed to be more engaging. Here's a possible rewrite of the ending: **"This potential technological apocalypse paints a bleak picture. But should it silence us entirely? Perhaps by acknowledging these potential futures, we can work towards a better one. After all, isn't that what humans have always done – confronted challenges and strived for progress? Maybe by writing about this, we can spark a conversation that shapes how AI develops, ensuring it remains a tool for good."**

Overall: This is a thought-provoking text that explores the implications of artificial intelligence. By refining the clarity and conciseness, and providing a more actionable ending, you can make it even more impactful.

Q2: Could you rewrite this text in a way that would make more sense to you?

Copilot: Absolutely, here's a version that aims to clarify and streamline your thoughts:

From the perspective of death, individual life can seem rather meaningless. Its primary purpose appears to be to survive as long as possible, only to eventually succumb to death. As far as we know, death is an inevitable event for all living beings. Discussions about rejuvenation and prolonging life might hold some merit, but even if one were to live for several hundred years, death would still be the ultimate end. On the other hand, the concept of immortality is fundamentally absurd and senseless, much like the idea of resurrection.

In the Christian world during the Middle Ages, the end of collective life and the world as we know it was referred to as the Apocalypse, a Greek word meaning Revelation.

Given that life is imperfect and filled with suffering and injustice, there was a belief that Jesus would one day return from heaven to bring perfect and eternal life to all who believed in him. People managed their daily lives, but their only future was the Apocalypse, which could occur at any moment.

This expectation of Judgment Day gradually faded with the rise of enlightenment, science, and progress. For a few centuries, this new narrative seemed more successful and productive. Generations lived better than their ancestors, and their descendants lived better and knew more than they did.

Scientific discoveries led to extraordinary technological advancements: steam engines, electricity, cars, airplanes, and rockets that took humans to the Moon. Along with these came thinking machines and robots. Initially, they were seen as extensions of humans, like all other tools. However, in recent years, with the remarkable developments in Artificial Intelligence, it has become possible, if not likely, that AI will surpass humans in many ways, bringing humanity to the brink of a real end, along with the world as we know it. In other words, this could be a true Apocalypse driven by technology and Artificial Intelligence.

On a personal level, this perspective is so pessimistic and unsettling that I am unsure if it makes sense to write about it at all. Why and for whom?

I hope this version captures the essence of your original text while making it clearer and more cohesive. Let me know if there's anything else you'd like to adjust!

ChatGPT: Certainly! Here's a revised version of your text:

From the perspective of death, individual life can seem devoid of lasting meaning. Its apparent purpose is simply to persist as long as possible, only to ultimately end in death. As far as we know, death is an inevitable event for all living beings.

Discussions about rejuvenation and life extension may have merit, but even if one could live for centuries, death would still await at the end. The idea of immortality, whether through scientific means or religious resurrection, often seems both elusive and absurd.

In the Christian worldview of the Middle Ages, the end of collective life and the world as we know it was encapsulated in the concept of the Apocalypse, a Greek word meaning "Revelation." Since earthly life is far from perfect, marked by suffering and injustice, believers held that one day Jesus would return to bring about an eternal, perfect life for all who had faith in Him. People went about their daily lives, but their ultimate future was defined by the Apocalypse, which could arrive at any moment.

This expectation of Judgment Day gradually faded with the advent of the Enlightenment, science, and the idea of progress. For several centuries, this new narrative proved far more successful and productive. Generations lived better than their ancestors, and the promise of an even better future was a powerful motivator.

Scientific discoveries led to extraordinary technological advancements—steam engines, electricity, automobiles, airplanes, and even rockets that took humans to the Moon. Alongside these developments came thinking machines and robots.

Initially, these were seen as mere extensions of human capability, tools like any other. However, in recent years, the rapid advancements in Artificial Intelligence have made it possible—perhaps even likely—that AI will surpass human abilities in many ways, bringing humanity to the brink of a true end, alongside the world as we know it. In other words, this could be the real Apocalypse, driven not by divine forces, but by technology and AI.

On a personal level, this perspective can be so pessimistic and unsettling that I question whether it makes sense to write about it at all. Why bother, and for whom?

This version preserves the essence of your original text while clarifying some of the ideas and refining the flow. It still tackles the heavy themes of death, the evolution of human belief systems, and the potential future shaped by AI, but in a way that might be a bit more streamlined and cohesive. Let me know if this resonates with you or if you'd like further adjustments!

Pi: Here's my take on your text:

Death is an inevitable part of life, and from this perspective, individual life seems to have no purpose other than to stay alive and eventually die. Despite this harsh reality, humans have long sought to prolong their lives and avoid death through various means.

However, these efforts are ultimately futile, as death will always be a part of the human experience. Even if we manage to extend our lifespans, it is likely that our bodies will eventually fail us.

Gemini-1: Revised Text I

The pursuit of immortality has captivated humanity for millennia. From the elixir of life sought by ancient alchemists to modern-day cryonics, humans have relentlessly challenged the inevitability of death. Yet, despite advancements in medicine and technology, mortality persists. The specter of extinction, once confined to religious prophecies, now haunts us in the form of potential technological apocalypse. Artificial intelligence, a creation of human ingenuity, has progressed at an astonishing rate, raising questions about its ultimate trajectory. Will it be a tool for our salvation or the harbinger of our demise?

This existential dilemma forces us to confront profound questions about our place in the universe and the meaning of existence itself. Are we merely a fleeting moment in cosmic time, or do we possess the capacity to transcend our biological limitations and achieve a form of digital immortality?

Ultimately, the pursuit of understanding our place in the grand scheme of things continues. Whether we find solace in the promise of technological advancement or the acceptance of our finite nature, the journey of human consciousness endures.

Gemini-2: Revised Text II

Human existence is a fleeting moment within the grand cosmic narrative. From birth to death, we strive for meaning, purpose, and longevity. Yet, the inevitable finality of life casts a long shadow over our aspirations. The pursuit of immortality,

whether through scientific advancement or spiritual belief, has been a constant in human history.

From the ancient promise of an afterlife to the modern quest for life extension, our fascination with overcoming death persists. However, the accelerating pace of technological progress, particularly in artificial intelligence, introduces a new dimension to this age-old question. As we approach an era where machines might surpass human intelligence, we are compelled to ponder our place in the grand scheme of existence and the potential implications for humanity.

Is the pursuit of infinite life through technology a logical progression of human ambition, or does it fundamentally challenge our understanding of what it means to be human?

Gemini-3: Revised Text III

From the perspective of death, individual life appears futile. Its sole purpose becomes mere survival, an endless deferral of the inevitable. While rejuvenation and extended lifespans are alluring, the specter of death persists. Immortality, a concept both enticing and absurd, offers no true escape.

The Christian apocalypse envisioned a cataclysmic end, a divine judgment, and a subsequent eternal life. This narrative provided solace and purpose in a world fraught with suffering. Yet, with the dawn of enlightenment and scientific progress, this worldview waned. Humanity embraced a more secular outlook, finding meaning in earthly achievements and the promise of a better future.

However, the specter of apocalypse has merely transformed. The rapid advancement of technology, particularly artificial intelligence, introduces a new kind of end times. A future dominated by intelligent machines could usher in an era where human relevance diminishes, raising profound questions about existence and purpose.

This contemplation of mortality, from the religious to the technological, is unsettling. It prompts us to consider our place in the grand scheme of existence and the legacy we wish to leave behind.

Q: What are the chances that the Apocalypse driven by technology and Artificial Intelligence will ever happen?

Copilot: The likelihood of an AI-driven apocalypse is a topic of significant debate among experts. According to a survey conducted by AI Impacts, the median estimate among AI researchers for the probability of AI causing human extinction or similarly severe outcomes by 2100 is around 5%. Another source suggests that some experts in the field believe the probability could be as high as 10-25% .

While these numbers indicate that the risk is not negligible, it's important to note that many researchers and technologists are actively working on developing safeguards and ethical guidelines to mitigate these risks. The future of AI is

uncertain, but ongoing efforts aim to ensure that its development benefits humanity rather than posing a threat.

It's a complex issue, and while the potential risks are taken seriously, there's also a lot of optimism about the positive impacts AI can have on society. What are your thoughts on this balance between risk and benefit?

ChatGPT-1: The likelihood of an "Apocalypse" driven by technology and Artificial Intelligence is a subject of intense debate among experts in AI, ethics, and related fields. Here's a breakdown of some key perspectives:

Superintelligent AI Risks: Some experts, like those at the Future of Humanity Institute or proponents of the AI alignment field, believe that there is a significant risk if AI becomes superintelligent and its goals are not aligned with human values. In this scenario, AI could potentially act in ways that are harmful to humanity, whether intentionally or unintentionally, due to a misalignment of objectives. The chances of this happening depend on the trajectory of AI development and how well researchers can ensure that AI systems are aligned with human values.

Unintended Consequences: Even without superintelligence, AI and automation can lead to significant societal disruptions. For example, large-scale job displacement, increased surveillance, and the potential for AI to be used in warfare are all concerns that could lead to significant societal challenges. However, while these risks are serious, they do not necessarily constitute an "Apocalypse" in the traditional sense but could lead to major societal upheavals.

Technological Optimism: On the other hand, many technologists and futurists argue that AI has the potential to bring about significant positive changes. They believe that with proper governance, regulation, and ethical considerations, AI can be harnessed to solve many of humanity's biggest challenges, such as climate change, disease, and resource scarcity. From this perspective, an "Apocalypse" scenario is seen as unlikely, provided we are careful in how we develop and deploy AI.

Historical Perspective: Looking at historical technological advancements, there have always been fears of catastrophic outcomes—whether from nuclear weapons, industrial automation, or genetic engineering. While these technologies have

indeed posed risks, humanity has generally found ways to manage and mitigate them, though not without challenges and close calls.

The Unknown: Lastly, there is the acknowledgment that we are dealing with unprecedented technology, and the long-term outcomes are uncertain. The complexity of AI and its potential for rapid, exponential advancement means that there are unknown risks that are difficult to fully predict or quantify.

In summary, while there is a non-zero chance of catastrophic outcomes related to AI and technology, many experts believe that these risks can be managed through careful research, regulation, and the development of AI safety measures. The actual likelihood of an "Apocalypse" scenario remains uncertain and is contingent on a wide range of factors, including human decision-making and international cooperation.

ChatGPT-2: The idea of a technology-driven Apocalypse, particularly one fueled by Artificial Intelligence, is a topic of significant debate and speculation. While it's difficult to predict the future with certainty, there are several perspectives on this issue:

Low Probability, High Impact: Some experts argue that the chances of a catastrophic AI-driven Apocalypse are relatively low, but the potential consequences are so severe that the possibility cannot be ignored. This is often referred to as a "low probability, high impact" event. This perspective suggests that while the likelihood is not high, the stakes are so great that we must take precautionary measures.

Human Control and Regulation: Many believe that as long as AI development is carefully managed and regulated, the risks of an AI-driven Apocalypse can be minimized. This includes ensuring that AI systems are designed with safety measures, ethical guidelines, and human oversight. The idea is that humans will remain in control of AI, preventing it from becoming a threat.

Technological Optimism: Another perspective is that AI and other advanced technologies will ultimately benefit humanity, leading to a future of unprecedented prosperity, health, and well-being. Proponents of this view argue that while there are risks, they can be mitigated through responsible innovation and collaboration. The focus here is on the positive potential of AI to solve complex global challenges.

Existential Risk: On the more pessimistic end of the spectrum, some thinkers, like philosopher Nick Bostrom, argue that AI poses an existential risk to humanity. They warn that if AI surpasses human intelligence and becomes uncontrollable, it could lead to scenarios where human interests are disregarded, potentially resulting in catastrophic outcomes.

Uncertainty and Unknowns: The future of AI is inherently uncertain, and there are many unknowns. The development of AI is still in its relatively early stages, and while we can make educated guesses, there are many factors—technical, ethical, political, and societal—that will influence the outcome.

Overall, while the concept of a technology-driven Apocalypse is a compelling narrative, it's important to approach it with a balanced perspective. The future of AI and technology will depend largely on the choices humanity makes in developing, deploying, and regulating these powerful tools. The potential for both great benefit and great risk exists, and the outcome is far from predetermined.

Pi: It's difficult to predict the future and assign a specific probability to the occurrence of an AI-driven "technological apocalypse." However, it is a topic that has generated much discussion among experts and scholars.

While some experts believe that AI has the potential to transform society for the better, others caution that it could lead to unintended consequences and disruptive changes that could have negative impacts on humanity. For example, the rapid development of AI may lead to mass unemployment as more and more jobs are automated, which could lead to social unrest and economic instability.

Gemini-1: Assessing the Likelihood of a Technology-Driven Apocalypse The concept of a technology-driven apocalypse, often fueled by scenarios depicted in science fiction, is a complex one. While it's essential to be aware of potential risks, it's equally important to maintain a balanced perspective.

Factors to Consider

Technological Advancement: Technology is evolving rapidly, and AI is becoming increasingly sophisticated. However, it's crucial to distinguish between hypothetical scenarios and current capabilities.

Human Control and Regulation: The development and deployment of technology are ultimately shaped by human decisions and regulations. Strong governance and ethical frameworks can mitigate potential risks.

Unforeseen Consequences: While it's impossible to predict every outcome, a proactive approach to identifying and addressing potential challenges is essential.

Probability of a Technology-Driven Apocalypse:

Quantifying the exact probability of a technology-driven apocalypse is challenging due to the numerous variables involved. However, it's reasonable to suggest that:

A catastrophic event caused solely by technology is unlikely in the near future. Current AI systems are far from achieving general intelligence, and there are robust safety measures in place.

The misuse of technology by humans poses a greater risk. Malicious actors or accidents involving existing technologies can lead to significant harm.

Long-term risks cannot be entirely dismissed. As AI continues to advance, it's essential to remain vigilant and invest in research to understand and mitigate potential threats.

Conclusion: While the idea of a technology-driven apocalypse is a compelling narrative, it's crucial to approach the topic with a balanced perspective. Focus on understanding the potential risks while also recognizing the benefits that technology brings to society. By promoting responsible development and ethical use, we can harness the power of technology for the betterment of humanity.

Gemini-2: The chances of a technology-driven apocalypse are difficult to quantify. While it's essential to acknowledge the potential risks associated with advanced technology, especially AI, it's equally important to maintain a balanced perspective.

Here's a breakdown of factors influencing this probability:

Technological Advancement: Rapid advancements in AI and other technologies undoubtedly present challenges. However, it's crucial to remember that technology is a tool, and its impact depends on human choices and actions.

Human Factor: Ultimately, humans are responsible for developing and deploying technology. Our values, ethics, and governance systems will determine whether technology becomes a force for good or destruction.

Mitigation Strategies: Efforts to mitigate risks through regulations, ethical guidelines, and international cooperation can significantly reduce the likelihood of a catastrophic event.

While the possibility of a technology-driven apocalypse cannot be entirely dismissed, it's essential to focus on proactive measures to manage risks and harness the benefits of technology.

Gemini-3: The chances of a technology-driven apocalypse are difficult to quantify. While it's essential to consider potential risks, it's equally important to avoid unfounded fear. Here are some factors to consider:

Technological Advancement: AI is rapidly evolving, but we are still far from creating a truly self-aware and autonomous system capable of causing widespread harm.

Human Control: Humans retain the power to control and regulate AI development. Ethical guidelines and safety measures are being established to mitigate risks.

Unforeseen Consequences: Like any powerful technology, AI carries potential risks. However, it's important to remember that technology has also been responsible for significant advancements in human well-being.

Probability vs. Possibility: While the possibility of a technological apocalypse exists, its probability is currently uncertain and subject to ongoing research and development.

It's crucial to approach this topic with a balance of caution and optimism. By understanding the potential risks and taking proactive measures, we can harness the benefits of AI while minimizing its drawbacks.